

Social

DISCIPLINARY AWARENESS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

School students need clear boundaries: boundaries that adults - parents as well as teachers - must set. We cannot abdicate our responsibility when students move outside those boundaries. To do that is to betray children, because the consequences of bad behaviour are so damaging It is the duty of the parents and teachers to create disciplinary awareness. The study aimed to examine the disciplinary awareness among secondary school students. The investigator adopted survey method to study the disciplinary awareness among school students. For this study a sample of 300 school students from 5 Govt and Private schools which are situated in and around Udumalpet town of Tirupur district in Tamil Nadu were selected by the investigator using simple random sampling technique. The findings reveal that 28.33% of the school students belong to low level of disciplinary awareness, 43.66% of school students the belong to moderate level of disciplinary awareness, 28% of school students belong to high level of disciplinary awareness. Also it is found that there is a significant difference in attitude towards disciplinary awareness between male and female among school students. Females possess better disciplinary awareness than male students.

Keywords: Disciplinary Awareness; School Students; Education & Behaviour.

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1. Introduction

The word 'discipline' comes from a Latin word "disciplinaire" which means "to impart education" or "to teach." The unfortunate thing is that many people associate the word with giving punishment which is actually a small part of the meaning. Discipline actually means to groom a person's behaviour, etiquette and entire personality. The emphasis in discipline, therefore, should be on improving performance or correcting an undesirable conduct rather than simply on punishing it. When a person is disciplined, he or she possesses the trait of being well-

behaved. In this context, the word discipline is related to the words conduct, behaviour and deportment. It is a vital aspect in the field of personality development. Discipline is actually a combination of reward and punishment methods. A child, if disciplined at an early age grows up to become a responsible, well-bred individual. A person who is competent, confident and caring is always known to have a disciplinary approach towards life.

Students have been into different information drive about the Institution such as the freshmen orientation and department, general assembly to inform their rights and duties as students. This concept is said to be students disciplinary awareness. Children need clear boundaries: boundaries that adults - parents as well as teachers - must set. We cannot abdicate our responsibility when children move outside those boundaries. To do that is to betray children, because the consequences of bad behaviour are so damaging. Of course we must keep a sense of proportion. To be disciplined is then, subject to context, either a virtue (the ability to follow instructions well) or a euphemism for punishment (which may also be referred to as disciplinary procedures). Disciplinary action is any action taken by the authority or higher official in response to an unsatisfactory employee performance or behaviour. A disciplinary procedure is a way that a teacher or higher official can tell the student that something is wrong. It also allows the teacher or higher official to explain clearly what improvement is needed and it should give the student an opportunity to explain their side of a situation. It can lead to disciplinary action. Every institution has disciplinary procedures which provide basic practical guidance to students, teachers and their representatives and set out principles for handling disciplinary and grievance situations in the school

School discipline is not a new phenomenon. Many researchers have documented ineffective discipline practices back to the beginning of United States schooling during early colonialism (Empey & Stafford, 1991; Greenberg, 1999; Regoli & Hewitt, 1997). According to Cole (1996), the aim of any disciplinary procedure is to correct unsatisfactory behaviour, rather than to punish. It should therefore, specify as fully as possible what constitutes 'misconduct' and what constitute 'gross misconduct' which calls for a stricter application of the procedure. The need for discipline arises when there is an unacceptable behaviour on the part of an employee (Cole, 1996). He stated that disciplinary matters have to be handled with fairness and credibly and as such employees should be given fair hearing.

2. Research Reviews

Mehrak Rahimi et.al., (2014) in their study investigated the role of EFL teachers' classroom discipline strategies in their teaching effectiveness and their students' motivation and achievement in learning English as a foreign language. 1408 junior high-school students expressed their perceptions of the strategies their English teachers used (punishment, recognition/reward, discussion, involvement, and aggression) to discipline the classroom. It was also revealed that in classes where teachers managed disruptive behaviors by using punitive strategies, students had problems in learning as punitive strategies lowered students' motivation. Teaching effectiveness was found to mediate the effect of punishment on motivation while motivation mediated the effect of punitive strategies on achievement.

O. Stanley Ehiane (2014) carried out a study to establish the relationships between schools discipline and students' academic performance. The study employed cross sectional research survey design in which questionnaire was the main instrument of data collection in addition to interview guide and document review. Simple percentage and Chi-square statistical method were used to analyze the data. However, the findings of the study clearly showed that effective school discipline should be encouraged in controlling students' behaviour thus affects students' general academic performance.

Seth Izen (2012) investigated how the childhood discipline practices of corporal punishment and inductive reasoning were related to the development of moral courage. Holocaust. University students completed an adult recall survey of their childhood discipline experiences and self-report tests for the components of moral courage. Significant positive correlations were found between childhood experiences of inductive discipline and moral courage. No significant relationship was found between childhood experiences of corporal punishment and moral courage

3. Research Design

The investigator adopted survey method to study the disciplinary awareness among secondary school students. For the study about the attitude towards disciplinary awareness among school students the sample size is 300 school students from 5 Govt and Private schools which are situated in and around Udumalpet town of Tirupur district in Tamil Nadu.

HYPOTHESIS 1:

There will be a difference in the level of attitude towards disciplinary awareness among school students.

Table 1: Frequency and percentage difference in the level of attitude towards disciplinary awareness among school students.

DISCIPLINARY AWARENESS								
Low			Moderate			High		
Q1	F	%	Q2	F	%	Q3	F	%
17	85	28.33%	20	131	43.66%	23	84	28%

Table 1 exhibits the result of attitude towards disciplinary awareness among school students. According to the table totally 28.33% of the school students belong to low level of disciplinary awareness, 43.66% of the school student belongs to moderate level of disciplinary awareness, 28% of the school students belong to high level of disciplinary awareness. So the hypothesis No: 1 is accepted. Thus it is inferred that there is a difference in the level of attitude towards disciplinary awareness among school students.

HYPOTHESIS 2:

There will be a significant mean score difference of attitude towards disciplinary awareness between male and female among school students.

Table 2: Means score difference and t-test of attitude towards disciplinary awareness between male and female among school students.

S.NO	GENDER	N	Mean	S.D	df	t-value	p-value	Result
1.	MALE	80	19.62	3.859	300	.940	.004	S
2.	FEMALE	220	20.03	3.096				
3.	TOTAL	300						

The **Table 2** shows that mean score difference in attitude towards disciplinary awareness between male and female among school students. The calculated t-value is statistically significant at 0.05 levels and hence, the hypothesis 2 is accepted. It can be concluded that there is a significant difference in attitude towards disciplinary awareness between male and female among school students.

CHART 1: MEAN SCORE DIFFERENCE IN ATTITUDE TOWARDS DISPLINARY AWARENESS AMONG STUDENTS BASED ON GENDER

The chart 4.1 shows that females possess better disciplinary awareness than male students.

HYPOTHESIS 3:

There will be a significant mean score difference of attitude towards disciplinary awareness between government and private school students.

Table 3: Mean score difference and t-test of attitude towards disciplinary awareness between government and private school students.

S.NO	TYPE OF SCHOOL	N	Mean	S.D	df	t-value	p-value	Result
1.	GOVT	105	19.82	3.438	300	.399	.582	N.S
2.	PRIVATE	195	19.98	3.254				
3.	TOTAL	300						

The **Table 3** shows that mean score difference in attitude towards disciplinary awareness between government and private school students. The calculated t-value is statistically not significant at 0.05 levels and hence, the hypothesis 3 is rejected. It can be concluded that there is no significant difference in attitude towards disciplinary awareness between government and private school students.

CHART 2: MEAN SCORE DIFFERENCE IN ATTITUDE TOWARDS DISPLINARY AWARENESS AMONG STUDENTS BASED ON TYPE OF SCHOOL

4. Conclusion

The findings reveal that 28.33% of the school students belong to low level of disciplinary awareness, 43.66% of school students the belong to moderate level of disciplinary awareness, 28% of school students belong to high level of disciplinary awareness. Also it is found that there is a significant difference in attitude towards disciplinary awareness between male and female among school students. Females possess better disciplinary awareness than male students.

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